

DOI: 10.15276/EJ.03.2025.1
 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17148142
 UDC: 339.138:316.77:378.014.6
 JEL: L84, M14

ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL MEDIA, BRAND IMAGE AND WORD OF MOUTH ON DECISIONS WITH ATTITUDE AS A MODERATING VARIABLE (CASE STUDY ON ECONOMICS FACULTY STUDENTS)

АНАЛІЗ ВПЛИВУ СОЦІАЛЬНИХ МЕРЕЖ, ІМІДЖУ БРЕНДУ ТА УСНОЇ РЕКЛАМИ НА РІШЕННЯ З УРАХУВАННЯМ СТАВЛЕННЯ ЯК МОДЕРУЮЧОЇ ЗМІННОЇ (ТЕМАТИЧНЕ ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ СТУДЕНТІВ ЕКОНОМІЧНОГО ФАКУЛЬТЕТУ)

Astrid Indah Lestari Tambunan
 University of Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia
 ORCID: 0000-0002-3565-5408

Syaifuddin
 University of Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia
 ORCID: 0000-0002-6977-5256

Salman Faris
 University of Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia
 ORCID: 0009-0000-6574-4316

Rosita
 University of Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia
 ORCID: 0000-0002-7961-7294

Received 17.07.2025

Astrid Indah Lestari Tambunan, Syaifuddin, Salman Faris, Rosita. Analiz vplivu socialnih mrezej, imidzu brendu ta usnoje reklami na risenja z urahovanjem stavljenja kak moderujuoj zminnoj (tematichne doslidzhenja studentiv ekonomichnogo fakul'tetu). Naukovo-metodichna stat'ja.

Це дослідження аналізує вплив соціальних мереж, іміджу бренду та усного поширення інформації на рішення студентів навчатися на економічному факультеті Університету Прима Індонезія, використовуючи Attitude як модератор. Учасники дослідження становили 4056 студентів, і за допомогою формули Hair було отримано вибірку зі 170 осіб. Дані були зібрані за допомогою інтерв'ю та анкетування, проаналізовані за допомогою Smart PLS. Результати показують, що соціальні мережі та усне поширення інформації мають позитивний та значний вплив на прийняття рішень, тоді як імідж бренду має позитивний, але незначний вплив. Attitude має значний прямий вплив, але не пом'якшує зв'язки між соціальними мережами/іміджем бренду та рішеннями, хоча він пом'якшує вплив усного поширення інформації. Значення R² показує, що 55,5% прийняття рішень пояснюється цими змінними, тоді як 44,5% залежить від інших факторів.

Ключові слова: ставлення, імідж бренду, вибір рішень, соціальні мережі та усне поширення інформації

Astrid Indah Lestari Tambunan, Syaifuddin, Salman Faris, Rosita. Analysis of Social Media, Brand Image and Word of Mouth on Decisions with Attitude as a Moderating Variable (Case Study on Economics Faculty Students). Scientific and methodical article.
 This study analyzes the influence of Social Media, Brand Image, and Word of Mouth on students' decisions to study at the Faculty of Economics, Prima Indonesia University, with Attitude as a moderator. The population was 4,056 students, and using the Hair formula, a sample of 170 was obtained. Data were collected through interviews and questionnaires, analyzed with Smart PLS. Results show Social Media and Word of Mouth have a positive and significant effect on decision-making, while Brand Image has a positive but insignificant effect. Attitude has a significant direct effect but fails to moderate the links between Social Media/Brand Image and decisions, though it moderates the effect of Word of Mouth. The R² value indicates that 55.5% of decision-making is explained by these variables, while 44.5% is influenced by other factors.

Keywords: attitudes, brand image, choosing decisions, social media and word of mouth

Higher Education as an important part of the world of education that is responsible for efforts to educate the nation's life has a very strategic responsibility and role to take part in overcoming problems in the quality of human resources. Government policies that provide the widest possible opportunity for all components of society to participate in educational development in Indonesia to empower community participation in organizing education based on the principle of autonomy in the context of a unitary state of the Republic of Indonesia, especially higher education (Sawaji, 2011).

Currently, many universities have opened undergraduate and postgraduate and doctoral programs. Medan as the capital city of North Sumatra Province is also the center of education in North Sumatra Province. Various

universities, academies, polytechnics, and colleges are scattered in several corners of North Sumatra. Universities in North Sumatra are fairly complete ranging from public to private universities with various study programs.

Prima Indonesia University is one of the universities in Medan which annually graduates students who take Stara 1 (S1), D4 and Diploma 3 (D3) study programs. Along with the increasing need for personnel, professionals and in order to develop the quality of education, the management of Prima Indonesia University opens various study programs in FE.

Based on data on the number of students admitted in 2021, 2022, 2023, there was a decrease in the number of students admitted in 2023. This of course has an impact on the income of FE Prima Indonesia University which in turn affects the operational costs in FE.

Social Media according to (Kotler, 2016) is a means for consumers who are used to view tourist panoramas through pictures and video information. Social Media is a website-based feature that can form networks and allow people to interact in a community. Through social media we can carry out various forms of exchange, collaboration and mutual acquaintance in written, visual and audiovisual forms. Like Twitter, Facebook, Blog, Foursquare, and others that are widely used today.

The next factor is Brand Image, Kotler (2017) states that Brand is the way people perceive (think about) the company or its products. Brand image can be considered as a type of association that comes to mind when consumers remember a particular brand.

The third factor is Word of Mouth. According to Jalilvand (2011) Word of Mouth is a process for consumers to exchange information and opinions related to products or services to others. As transitions occur, especially in the fields of technology and information, the concept of Word of Mouth develops and gives birth to concepts that are in accordance with the changes themselves. Word of Mouth has an important role in the consumer decision-making process by influencing consumer choices.

The main part

RESEARCH METHOD.

The population in this study are all FE students of Prima Indonesia University who were accepted in 2021-2023, totaling 4,056 students.

The sample taken from the population must be truly representative (Sugiyono, 2014). Given the large population, the sample formula used is using the Hair et al (2019) formula as follows:

$$N = 5-10 \times \text{the number of indicators used,}$$

$$N = 10 \times 17,$$

$$N = 170 \text{ people/sample.}$$

In this case, the researchers obtained it using a questionnaire distributed directly to FE students at Prima Indonesia University. In this study, the data sources used are primary data and secondary data.

Research Model. Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA).

The multiple linear regression method in this study uses the help of Smart PLS. The equation model used (Sugiyono, 2014), namely:

$$Y = a + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_1 X_2 X_3 + \epsilon,$$

where Y = Decision to Choose,

a = Constant,

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = X Variable Coefficient,

β_4 = Moderation Variable Coefficient,

X1 = Social Media,

X2 = Brand Image,

X3 = Word of Mouth,

ϵ = Standard Error (Residual).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Characteristics of Respondents Based on Gender.

The characteristics of respondents based on gender can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Gender

Age	Frequency	Percentage
21-25	114	67.1%
26-30	50	29.4%
>30	6	3.5%
Total	170	100%

Source: authors' own elaboration

Based on Table 1 of 170 respondents in FE students at Prima Indonesia University, the majority were aged 21-25 years as many as 114 people with a percentage of 67.1% and the lowest were aged > 30 as many as 6 people with a percentage of 3.5%.

Table 2. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Education

Education	Frequency	Percentage
D3	5	2.9%
S1	157	92.4%
S2	8	4.7%
Total	145	100%

Source: authors' own elaboration

Based on Table 2 of 170 respondents in FE students at Prima Indonesia University, the majority had an undergraduate education as many as 157 people with a percentage of 92.4% and the lowest had a D3 education as many as 5 people with a percentage of 2.9%.

Table 3. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Visits

Number of Visits	Frequency	Percentage
1	0	0%
>5	135	79.4%
2-5	35	20.6%
Total	145	100%

Source: authors' own elaboration

Based on Table 3 of 170 respondents at FE Prima Indonesia University students, it is known that 135 people have visited FE University > 5 times with a percentage of 79.4% and 35 other people have visited 2-5 times with a percentage of 20.6%.

Table 4. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	77	45,2%
Female	93	54,8%
Total	170	100%

Source: authors' own elaboration

Based on Table 4 of 170 respondents at FE Prima Indonesia University students, it is known that the majority of respondents are female as many as 93 people with a percentage of 54.8% and 77 men with a percentage of 45.3%.

Inner Model Test.

Test the Correlation of Variables in the Structural Model.

According to Hair et al., (2018) multicollinearity test to provide a perspective on the impact of collinearity on exogenous variables in the structural model.

Table 5. Collinearity Statistic

	Brand Image	Choosing Decision	Attitude	Social Media	Word of Mouth
Brand Image		1.648			
Attitude		2.248			
Social Media		2.162			
Word of Mouth		1.552			

Source: authors' own elaboration

Model Quality Test.

The R Square value on Attitude is 0.578 or 57.8%, which means that Social Media, Brand Image, and Word of Mouth are able to explain Attitude by 57.8%, which means that this model is in the strong category, while the remaining 42.2% is explained by other factors outside the model, and the R Square value on the Decision to Choose is 0.55 or 55%, which means that Social Media, Brand Image, Word of Mouth, and Attitude are able to explain the Decision to Choose by 55%, which is in the strong category, while the remaining 45% is explained by other factors outside the model, indicating a strong model.

Table 6. R Square

	R Square
Choosing Decision	0.551

Source: authors' own elaboration

f Square (Effect Size).

The value of f Square or the largest effect size is Attitude towards the Decision to Choose, which is 0.130 including the medium category, and the one with the smallest effect size value is Word of Mouth on the Decision to Choose, which is 0.023 including the small category.

Table 7. f Square

	Brand Image	Choosing Decision	Attitude	Social Media	Word of Mouth
Brand Image		0.026			
Decision to Choose					
Attitude		0.130			
Social Media		0.067			
Word of Mouth		0.023			

Source: authors' own elaboration

Moderation Significance Test.

Table 8. Path Coefficient

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Social Media -> Choosing Decision	0.226	0.197	0.113	1.996	0.046
Brand Image -> Decision to Choose	0.140	0.143	0.084	1.666	0.096
Word of Mouth -> Choosing Decision	0.142	0.154	0.060	2.381	0.018
Attitude -> Decision to Choose	0.372	0.382	0.078	4.764	0.000
S_SM -> Choosing Decision	-0.032	-0.031	0.088	0.367	0.714
S_BI -> Decision to Choose	-0.040	-0.036	0.110	0.367	0.713
S_WOM -> Choosing Decision	-0.105	-0.127	0.056	1.879	0.061

Source: authors' own elaboration

The following is the interpretation of Table 8 as follows:

1. It is known that the MRA Social Media coefficient value is 0.226, which is positive, with a significance of 5% t count $1.996 > 1.96$ and a p value of $0.046 < \alpha (0.05)$, meaning that Social Media has a positive and significant effect on Voting Decisions. This means that the better the utilization of Social Media, the more significant the voting decision will be.

2. It is known that the MRA Brand Image coefficient value is 0.140, which is positive, with a significance of 5% t count $1.666 < 1.96$ and a p value of $0.096 < \alpha (0.05)$, meaning that Brand Image has a positive and insignificant effect on voting decisions. This means that the better the Brand Image, the more insignificant the Choosing Decision will be.

3. It is known that the MRA Word of Mouth coefficient value is 0.142, which is positive, with a significance of 5% t count $2.381 > 1.96$ and a p value of $0.018 < \alpha (0.05)$, meaning that Word of Mouth has a positive and significant effect on the Choosing Decision. This means that the better the Word of Mouth, the more significant the Choosing Decision will be.

4. It is known that the MRA coefficient value of the attitude pathway on the decision to choose is 0.372, which is positive, with a significance of 5% t count $4.764 > 1.96$ and a p value of $0.000 < \alpha (0.05)$, meaning that attitude has a positive and significant influence on the decision to choose. This means that the better the attitude possessed by students, it will significantly increase the decision to choose.

5. It is known that the path coefficient value of Social Media on the Decision to Choose through Attitude is -0.032, which is negative, with a significance of 10% t count $0.367 < 1.96$ and a p value of $0.714 > \alpha (0.1)$. This means that attitude is unable to moderate the relationship between social media and voting decisions.

6. It is known that the path coefficient value of Brand Image on the Decision to Choose through Attitude is -0.040, which is negative, with a significance of 10% t count $0.367 < 1.96$ and a p value of $0.713 > \alpha (0.1)$. This means that attitude is unable to moderate the relationship between Brand Image and Choosing Decision.

7. It is known that the path coefficient value of Word of Mouth on the Decision to Choose is -0.105, which is negative, with a significance of 10% t count $1.879 < 1.96$ and a p value of $0.061 < \alpha (0.1)$. This means that attitude is able to moderate the relationship between Word of Mouth on Choosing Decisions.

DISCUSSION. The Effect of Social Media on Voting Decisions.

According to Eka (2014) Social media is a social network that can be used to market media products that can be used, one of which is Facebook, Twitter and Kaskus. And social networks can be said to be an effective communication media tool for companies to be able to interact with their consumers and be able to become a strategic tool with Word of Mouth. Social Media according to (Kotler, 2016) is a means for consumers who are used to see tourist panoramas through pictures and video information. Social Media is a website-based feature that can form networks and allow people to interact in a community. Through social media we can carry out various forms of exchange, collaboration and mutual acquaintance in written, visual and audiovisual forms. Such as Twitter, Facebook, Blog, Foursquare, and others that are widely used today. Meanwhile, according to (Dixon, 2012), explaining the definition of social media involves the use of web-based technology to turn one-way communication into an online interactive dialog. With the existence of social media in the current era of digitalization, it will certainly affect students' decisions in choosing a college because of the information spread on social media.

Conclusions

The Effect of Brand Image on Choosing Decisions.

Kotler (2017) states that image is the way consumers perceive (think about) the company or its products. Brand image can be considered as a type of association that comes to mind when consumers remember a particular brand. A brand is a label that is appropriate and appropriate to describe a marketed object. Meanwhile, according to (Aaker, 2017), a brand is a distinguishing name and or symbol (such as a logo, stamp, or packaging) with the intention of identifying goods or services from a seller or a certain group of sellers, thereby distinguishing it from goods and services produced by competitors. The quality and popularity of a brand from a university will certainly influence students in their decision to choose a college.

The Effect of Word of Mouth on Choosing Decisions.

According to Kotler and Keller (2016) Word of Mouth (WOM) is a powerful marketing tool and is one of the most effective sales drivers, along with advertising awareness. Some brands have been built almost exclusively by word of mouth. Word of mouth marketing finds ways to engage customers so that they will choose to speak positively with others about products, services and brands. Viral marketing encourages people to exchange information online related to products or services. However, digitalization is a form of very rapid technological development whose main purpose is to provide convenience and efficiency in various aspects, such as efficiency in energy, costs and procedures.

The Influence of Attitude on Choosing Decisions.

The existence of social media, its use, utilization, and the quality of a brand and the conversations that occur (word of mouth) among students will certainly thoroughly influence students in determining and shaping student attitudes in the decision to choose college. This is because the decision to choose by consumers is not only influenced by one cause but there are other causes for consumers to make choices in decision making.

The Effect of Social Media on Choosing Decisions through Attitudes

According to Abdullah and Tantri (2016) attitudes explain the cognitive evaluation, emotional feelings, and action tendencies of someone who likes or dislikes certain objects or ideas. People have attitudes towards all things such as religion, politics, clothing, music, food, etc. The existence of social media, its utilization and use in

providing information related to a product will certainly shape students' attitudes in making decisions before finally choosing to study at a university.

The Effect of Brand Image on Choosing Decisions through Attitudes.

Kotler and Keller (2017) define that Brand Image is the consumer's response to the overall offering provided by the company. Brand Image is an important driver of prospective and current customer behavior. All companies strive to build a strong and favorable brand image. Brand Image is an expression that is largely replaced by brand equity over time. Brand Image is the perception and belief made by consumers, as reflected in the associations that occur in consumers' memories. Brand Image is a set of brand associations that occur in consumers' memories that create a positive impression. The perceptions or responses that exist in the minds of students regarding the Brand Image of a University will certainly form an attitude in choosing before finally actually choosing to study at the University.

The Effect of Word of Mouth on Choosing Decisions through Attitudes.

According to Kotler and Keller (2016) Word of Mouth (WOM) is a powerful marketing tool and is one of the most effective sales drivers, along with advertising awareness. Some brands have been built almost exclusively by word of mouth. Word of mouth marketing finds ways to engage customers so that they will choose to speak positively with others about products, services and brands. Viral marketing encourages people to exchange information online related to the product or service.

Universities are expected to utilize Social Media, Brand Image, Attitude and Choice decisions in analyzing needs and markets.

Abstract

This research aims to determine and analyze the influence of Social Media, Brand Image and Word of Mouth on Students' Decisions to Choose to Study at the Faculty of Economics, Prima Indonesia University, moderated by Attitude. The population in this study was 4,056 students. Sample determination was carried out using the Hair formula so that a sample of 170 students was obtained.

Research data was obtained through interviews and distributing questionnaires. The data analysis technique was carried out using Smart PLS. Research results sourced from Smart PLS data processing show that Social Media has a positive and significant effect on voting decisions. Brand Image has a positive and insignificant effect on Choosing Decisions. Word of Mouth has a positive and significant effect on voting decisions. Attitude has a positive and significant effect on voting decisions. Attitudes of inability to moderate the relationship between Social Media and Voting Decisions.

An attitude of inability to moderate the relationship between Brand Image and Voting Decisions. Attitude is able to moderate the relationship between Word of Mouth and Voting Decisions. The coefficient of determination (R²) based on the R Square test results shows that 55.5% of the choice decision can be explained by the independent variables, namely Social Media, Brand Image and Word of Mouth, while the remaining 44.5 percent is explained by other factors outside this research model.

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Посилання на статтю:

Astrid Indah Lestari Tambunan. *Analysis of Social Media, Brand Image and Word of Mouth on Decisions with Attitude as a Moderating Variable (Case Study on Economics Faculty Students) / Astrid Indah Lestari Tambunan, Syaifuddin, Salman Faris, Rosita // Економічний журнал Одеського політехнічного університету. – 2025. – № 3(33). – С. 5-11. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.net.ua/ejopu/2025/No3/5.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/EJ.03.2025.1. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17148142.*

Reference a Journal Article:

Astrid Indah Lestari Tambunan. *Analysis of Social Media, Brand Image and Word of Mouth on Decisions with Attitude as a Moderating Variable (Case Study on Economics Faculty Students) / Astrid Indah Lestari Tambunan, Syaifuddin, Salman Faris, Rosita // Economic journal Odessa polytechnic university. – 2025. – № 3(33). – P. 5-11. – Retrieved from <https://economics.net.ua/ejopu/2025/No3/5.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/EJ.03.2025.1. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17148142.*

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